

AN EXAMINATION OF SUSTAINABILITY STUDIES IN THE UZBEKISTAN ENERGY SECTOR WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABILITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Prof. Dr. Öznur BOZKURT

Düzce University, Faculty of Business
Administration, Düzce, Türkiye

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ali KONAK

Karabük University, Faculty of Economics
and Administrative Sciences, Economics,
Karabük, Turkey

Abstract. This study aims to comparatively examine the sustainability performance of Uzbekneftegaz, Thermal Power Plants JSC, and National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan, the main companies operating in the Uzbek energy sector, within the framework of environmental, social, and economic dimensions. A qualitative analysis method was adopted in the research, and the fields of activity and sustainability practices of the relevant institutions were evaluated through literature and secondary data sources. The findings show that the Uzbek energy sector largely exhibits a fossil fuel-based structure, but the transition process to renewable energy has accelerated in recent years. Among the companies examined, Uzbekneftegaz was found to demonstrate strong performance in terms of economic sustainability, Thermal Power Plants JSC implemented efficiency-focused transformations in energy production, and National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan played a critical role in renewable energy integration and infrastructure development processes.

Keywords: Sustainability, Economic Development, Sustainability Report, Uzbekistan Energy Sector.

Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekiston energetika sektorida faoliyat yurituvchi asosiy kompaniyalar bo'lgan "O'zbekneftegaz", "Issiqlik elektr stansiyalari" AJ va "O'zbekiston milliy elektr tarmog'i"ning barqarorlik ko'rsatkichlarini ekologik, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy jihatlar doirasida qiyosiy o'rganishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqotda sifatli tahlil usuli qo'llanildi va tegishli muassasalarning faoliyat sohalari va barqarorlik amaliyotlari adabiyotlar va ikkilamchi ma'lumotlar manbalari orqali baholandi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekiston energetika sektori asosan qazilma yoqilg'iga asoslangan tuzilishga ega, ammo so'nggi yillarda qayta tiklanadigan energiyaga o'tish jarayoni tezlashdi. Tekshirilgan kompaniyalar orasida "O'zbekneftegaz" iqtisodiy barqarorlik nuqtai nazaridan yuqori ko'rsatkichlarni namoyish etgani, "Issiqlik elektr stansiyalari" AJ energiya ishlab chiqarishda samaradorlikka yo'naltirilgan o'zgarishlarni amalga oshirganligi va "O'zbekiston milliy elektr tarmog'i" qayta tiklanadigan energiya integratsiyasi va infratuzilmani rivojlantirish jarayonlarida muhim rol o'ynaganligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: Barqarorlik, Iqtisodiy rivojlanish, Barqarorlik to'g'risidagi hisobot, O'zbekiston energetika sektori

АННОТАЦИЯ. Целью данного исследования является сравнительное изучение показателей устойчивого развития компаний «Узбекнефтегаз», АО «Тепловые электростанции» и «Национальная электросеть Узбекистана», основных предприятий энергетического сектора Узбекистана, в рамках экологического, социального и экономического аспектов. В исследовании был использован качественный метод анализа, а сферы деятельности и практика устойчивого развития соответствующих учреждений оценивались на основе литературных и вторичных источников данных. Результаты показывают, что энергетический сектор Узбекистана в значительной степени основан на ископаемом топливе, но процесс перехода к возобновляемым источникам энергии ускорился в последние годы. Среди исследованных компаний «Узбекнефтегаз» продемонстрировал высокие показатели экономической устойчивости, АО «Тепловые

электростанции» реализовало преобразования в производстве энергии, ориентированные на повышение эффективности, а «Национальная электросеть Узбекистана» сыграла решающую роль в интеграции возобновляемых источников энергии и развитии инфраструктуры. В заключение установлено, что трансформация в сторону устойчивого развития в энергетическом секторе Узбекистана имеет многомерную структуру, и что инфраструктура передачи энергии и инвестиции в возобновляемые источники энергии играют особенно важную роль в этой трансформации. Данное исследование призвано внести вклад в литературу, предложив сравнительный взгляд на устойчивость энергетического сектора в развивающихся странах.

Ключевые слова: Устойчивое развитие, Экономическое развитие, Доклад об устойчивом развитии, Энергетический сектор Узбекистана.

1. Introduction. The sustainable use of energy resources and natural resources such as water and soil is important for the conservation of resources for future generations. Sustainability aims to ensure that existing natural resources are available for future generations. This includes preventing the overuse and waste of resources, maintaining the balance of ecosystems, and ensuring the sustainability of biodiversity. Sustainable resource management includes policies such as energy conservation, shifting towards renewable energy sources, efficient water use, protection of agricultural areas, and prevention of soil erosion. The principle of sustainability emphasizes avoiding the overconsumption of resources. This includes saving energy, reducing waste, promoting recycling, and creating policies to protect water and natural resources. At the same time, sustainability also includes measures such as making production processes more efficient and using technologies that are less harmful to the environment (Haessler, 2020). This approach aims for the sustainable use of natural resources in the long term and leaving a livable environment for future generations. The conscious and efficient use of resources is one of the fundamental principles of sustainability and aims to ensure the conservation of resources while considering the needs of future generations (Evli et al., 2018).

Sustainability focuses on balancing economic growth with environmental and social benefits for a more sustainable future by working in harmony with economic efficiency. This perspective allows businesses to both increase their competitive advantage and contribute to the environment and society by combining their economic profitability goals with the principle of sustainability. This study will address sustainability, its importance, and sustainable development. After a review of the relevant literature, findings on the sustainability activities of companies operating in the energy sector in Uzbekistan will be presented. Based on document analysis, data will be taken from the sustainability reports published by the companies, and inferences will be made regarding the activities carried out in the field of sustainability. In this context, based on the results obtained, recommendations will be made regarding the determination of the sustainability focus and the conduct of activities within this scope.

2. Sustainability. As a concept, sustainability is defined as the preservation and continuation of the current state of affairs. Human behavior is at the heart of sustainability (Akgül, 2010: 134). Sustainability is a way of thinking where individuals cooperate and seek solutions to social and economic problems through this cooperation. This concept imposes responsibility on individuals in economic, social, and environmental areas and requires decision-making with future generations in mind (Jones et al., 2008: 125). Sustainability is the effort to ensure that the resources currently available will also exist in the future. It is about striking a balance between meeting the needs of the day without compromising them and not wasting the resources of the future for the needs of the present. In the literature on sustainability, this concept is addressed in three dimensions: economic, social, and environmental.

Economic sustainability includes the protection of natural capital, which is a fundamental element for sustainable economic growth. The focus of economic sustainability is on developing environmental protection policies to conserve natural capital that is degraded and consumed within the economic system, preventing inefficient resource use, eliminating pollution, and creating an economy that benefits from technological innovations (Msengi et al., 2019). The main

goal is to aim for economic growth that is best for humanity and to ensure the sustainability of this economic growth (Basiago, 1998). Economic sustainability can be achieved by promoting the use of renewable energy sources, establishing a balance between economic activities and the natural environment, ensuring resource efficiency, and most importantly, addressing the transformation of the economic system with an environmentally conscious approach.

Social sustainability focuses on fundamental issues such as ensuring that all segments of society benefit from services without discrimination, creating safe living spaces, ensuring job security, increasing economic well-being, and implementing human rights practices equitably for all individuals. Social sustainability is about maintaining social and cultural traditions, creating a livable world, and ensuring that all humanity benefits equally from the advantages this world provides. Social sustainability focuses on issues such as fair distribution of income, equality in employment, democracy, and human rights (Vallance et al., 2011). Education, basic infrastructure, justice, freedom, malnutrition, housing, and health problems are important factors in achieving social sustainability (Bramley and Power, 2009). Environmental sustainability is about using resources without disrupting the functioning of the ecological system and transferring these resources efficiently to future generations (Tıraş, 2012: 61). Environmental sustainability, which aims to strike a balance between avoiding disruption of the natural environment and meeting human needs (Morelli, 2011: 5), includes activities such as preventing waste from harming the environment, shifting towards renewable resources, and striving for a clean environment (Kaypak, 2011: 26). Environmental sustainability is based on considering the environmental impacts of production and consumption activities and ensuring the efficient use of resources provided by the environment.

3. Sustainable Development. Sustainability focuses on balancing economic growth with environmental and social benefits for a more sustainable future, working in harmony with economic efficiency. This perspective allows businesses to both increase their competitive advantage and contribute to the environment and society by combining their economic profitability goals with the principle of sustainability. Sustainability aims to both improve the quality of life of current generations and ensure that future generations can meet their needs. It is seen as being of great importance in creating a long-term and healthy world by maintaining environmental, social and economic balance (Akgül et al., 2010). The primary goal of sustainable development is to meet the basic needs of the poorest segments of the world. This includes vital human needs such as food, water, shelter, health and education. At the heart of sustainable development lies the idea of prioritizing these needs with the principle of justice and equality (Guerra et al., 2022). Sustainable development is based on the idea that environmental resources are limited and that these resources must be managed sustainably. The concept of scarcity emphasizes the need for the intelligent use of environmental resources to meet the needs of present and future generations. This approach also considers the impact of advanced technology and social organization on the sustainability of environmental resources (Li et al., 2020). Sustainable development has a long-term and inclusive perspective, encompassing economic growth, increased social welfare, and environmental protection. This concept emphasizes the necessity of considering the needs of future generations while meeting the current needs of people (Dalğıç et al., 2018). Economic sustainability means the balanced use of resources and the preservation of economic opportunities for future generations (Wheeler, 2013). In this context, raising awareness about sustainable consumption habits and the environmental and social impacts of economic activities is an important part of the economic dimension. Encouraging individuals and institutions to use resources efficiently and adopt sustainable production and consumption habits are examples of this dimension (Hinton and Goodman, 2010). Awareness of economic sustainability emphasizes the importance of fair trade and income inequality. In this context, issues such as income distribution justice, fair use of resources, and social responsibility in trade are also considered within economic awareness. In this way, the aim is to achieve a balance between economic development and environmental and social impacts (Arnould et al., 2009). Sustainability encourages the development of green technologies. These technologies offer

innovative solutions in areas such as environmentally friendly energy production, waste management, and the use of renewable resources. This both reduces environmental impacts and provides economic benefits. Sustainability encourages the adoption of methods that will reduce environmental impacts and consume fewer natural resources in production processes. Measures such as producing less waste, recycling practices, and the use of renewable energy are part of sustainable production processes (Tseng et al., 2013). The most important factor in sustainable development is entrepreneurship and the sustainability-oriented decisions that entrepreneurs will make. Sustainability-oriented entrepreneurship refers to the activities of entrepreneurs who adopt sustainability principles in the business world and develop business models and practices that take into account environmental, social, and economic impacts. Sustainable entrepreneurship focuses on business models that, in addition to generating profit, are environmentally conscious, have a social impact, and adhere to the principle of long-term sustainability (Balli, 2019).

Sustainable entrepreneurs design their business models to minimize environmental impacts such as the conservation of natural resources, energy efficiency, and waste reduction (Keskin, 2016). They aim to create a positive impact on society and develop business models that address social problems. Sustainable entrepreneurs build their business models for long-term economic sustainability. This includes the ability to maintain the financial resilience and stability of the company in addition to generating revenue. These entrepreneurs design their business model and value chain in accordance with the principle of sustainability. They optimize processes such as the supply chain, product design, and distribution by considering environmental and social impacts (Bals and Tate, 2018). Sustainable entrepreneurship aims to strike a balance between environmental, social, and economic values in the business world. Such ventures aim for long-term success by contributing to both the business world and society with innovative and sustainable solutions. Ensuring social justice, equality, access to healthcare, and educational opportunities. This includes issues such as increasing the overall well-being of society and improving the quality of life (Cusack, 2019). An economically sustainable structure supports economic growth, employment, and income distribution. Efficient use of resources and sustainable economic activities without harming the environment ensures long-term economic stability (Jänicke, 2012). Sustainability requires responsibility at a global level. Countries, companies, and individuals must act in accordance with sustainability principles and develop solutions at a global level.

4. Findings On Sustainability Activities Of Energy Companies Operating In Uzbekistan.

The energy sector in Uzbekistan is largely based on natural gas and is transforming. In recent years, investments in solar and wind energy (e.g., ACWA Power, Masdar projects) have been rapidly increasing. State-owned companies or large-scale public-private partnerships largely run the energy sector in Uzbekistan. This section will examine the sustainability activities of three of the largest energy companies operating in Uzbekistan. The three largest and most influential energy companies are:

1. Uzbekneftegaz (UNG): It is Uzbekistan's national oil and gas company. It single-handedly produces the majority of the country's natural gas. It is a large energy company that has also been ranked globally. It carries out exploration, production, refining, and petrochemical activities.

2. Thermal Power Plants JSC (Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari): This is Uzbekistan's largest electricity generation company. It controls approximately 70% of the country's electricity generation capacity and operates thermal power plants, primarily powered by natural gas.

3. National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan (NEGU): This is the country's national electricity transmission and grid operator. It distributes energy received from electricity producers throughout the country and manages the main transmission infrastructure. Large-scale energy projects (especially renewable investments) play a critical role.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Sustainability Efforts of Energy Companies

n	Dimensio	Uzbekneftegaz	JSC	Thermal Power Plants	National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan
	Environmental	- Methane emission reduction projects in natural gas - Prevention of gas leaks - Energy efficiency investments - Carbon-intensive production (weakness)		- Modernization of old thermal power plants - Use of more efficient gas turbines - Emission reduction projects - High dependence on fossil fuels	- Reduction of grid losses and leakages - Renewable energy integration (solar/wind) - Smart grid investments
	Social	- High employment capacity - Employee training programs - Occupational health and safety practices - Support projects for local communities		- Technical personnel training - Improvements in occupational safety - Social contribution through energy supply security	- Increasing national energy access - Electricity access to rural areas - Public service role in energy infrastructure
c	Economic	- Accounts for a significant share of export revenues - Provides high foreign currency inflow - Strong contribution to the state budget		- Bears the main load of electricity generation - Provides critical energy for industry - Aims to reduce costs through efficiency improvements	- Backbone of the energy system - Critical role in attracting investments - Provides infrastructure for renewable projects
s	Strengths	-Economic katki ve enerjisi arzi		-Central role in electricity generation	-Renewable energy integration
	Weaknesses	-High carbon intensity		Dependence on fossil fuels	-Does not produce energy directly (indirect impact)
	Distinctive Aspect	-Focus on fossil fuel production and export		-Emphasis on efficiency improvement and plant modernization	-Actor building the infrastructure of energy transition

Uzbekistan's energy sector is undergoing a transition from a fossil fuel-based structure to renewable energy. Uzbekneftegaz is strong in economic sustainability. Thermal power plants are critical in operational efficiency and are pioneers in electricity generation. NEGU stands out as a key player in the environmental transformation. The greatest potential for transformation in terms of sustainability lies in the area of grid and renewable energy integration.

Conclusion. In this study, the sustainability performance of Uzbekneftegaz, Thermal Power Plants JSC, and National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan, operating in the Uzbek energy sector, was comparatively examined within the framework of environmental, social, and economic dimensions. The findings reveal that the country's energy sector is still largely based on fossil fuels, but policies and investments towards energy transformation have been accelerating in recent years. In the environmental dimension, while significant steps have been taken, particularly in reducing carbon emissions and increasing energy efficiency, the continued dependence on fossil fuels stands out as a fundamental limitation in terms of sustainability. In this context, it is observed that production-oriented companies have a higher environmental impact, while transmission and infrastructure-oriented structures play a more strategic role in terms of renewable energy integration. When evaluated in the social dimension, it is understood that energy

companies make significant contributions in areas such as job creation, providing technical training, and increasing access to energy. In particular, expanding energy access on a national scale is a critical element in increasing social welfare. Economically, the energy sector is one of the fundamental dynamics of the Uzbek economy, and the companies examined have a decisive impact on the country's revenues, industrial production, and investment attraction capacity. This demonstrates that the energy sector is a strategic area in the sustainability transformation, not only in terms of environmental factors but also in terms of economic stability. Overall, it has been concluded that the sustainability transformation in the Uzbek energy sector is a multi-dimensional and phased process; in this process, production, transmission, and distribution activities form a complementary structure. In the coming period, increasing renewable energy investments, reducing carbon intensity, and expanding corporate sustainability practices are critically important for the sector to achieve a more balanced and sustainable structure. In this regard, strengthening coordination among policymakers and sector stakeholders is considered one of the key factors that will directly affect the success of the sustainable energy transformation. The recommendations presented within the scope of the research can be summarized as follows: Public-private partnerships should be encouraged, especially for solar and wind energy projects. In this way, dependence on fossil fuels can be reduced and environmental sustainability can be strengthened. Systematic practices for measuring, reporting, and reducing carbon footprints should be widespread in production-oriented companies, primarily Uzbekneftegaz. Modernization of older power plants within Thermal Power Plants JSC should be accelerated, and the transition to high-efficiency production technologies should be supported. Under the leadership of the National Electric Grid of Uzbekistan, smart grid applications should be widespread to facilitate renewable energy integration and minimize transmission losses. Companies should be encouraged to regularly report their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance, and compliance with international standards (e.g., GRI) should be increased. The competencies of energy sector employees in sustainability, digitalization, and new energy technologies should be enhanced, and continuous training programs should be developed. The state needs to create incentive mechanisms to support the energy transition, improve the investment environment, and increase sustainability-oriented regulations. Overall, the success of the sustainability transformation in the Uzbek energy sector depends on the adoption of technological innovations, the development of institutional capacity, and the effectiveness of public-private partnerships. In this context, the implementation of the proposed strategies will significantly contribute to making the sector more sustainable, both environmentally and economically.

References

- Akgül, U. (2010). Sustainable development: The field of action of applied anthropology. *Ankara University Faculty of Language and History Geography Anthropology Journal*, (24), 133-164.
- Arnould, E. J., Plastina, A., & Ball, D. (2009). Does fair trade deliver on its core value proposition? Effects on income, educational attainment, and health in three countries. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 28(2), 186-201. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.28.2.186>
- Ballı, A. (2019). Sustainability, sustainable entrepreneurship and sustainable entrepreneurship in Turkey. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 11(29), 464-483. <https://doi.org/10.20875/makusobed.586555>
- Bals, L., & Tate, W. L. (2018). Sustainable supply chain design in social businesses: advancing the theory of supply chain. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 39(1), 57-79. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbl.12172>
- Basiago, A.D. (1998). Economic, social and environmental sustainability in development theory and urban planning practice. *Environmentalist*, 19, 145-161, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006697118620>